

weathering steels // Corrosion Science, № 74, 2013, pp 424 – 429

11. Qiang Yu, Xiaoyu Yang, Wangyue Dong, Qingfeng Wang, Fucheng Zhang, Xiaoyong Gu. Layer-by-layer investigation of the multilayer corrosion products for different Ni content weathering steel via a novel Pull-off testing // Corrosion Science, № 195, 2022, № 109988

12. W.K. Boyd, Corrosion of metals in the atmosphere // Metals and Ceramics Information Center, Columbus, 1974, pp. 1-18

13. J.A. Mejía Gómez, J. Antonissen, C.A. Palacio, E. De Grave. Effects of Si as alloying element on corrosion resistance of weathering steel // Corrosion Science, № 198, 2012, pp. 198-203

14. Rui Cao, Cheng Han, Xili Guo, Yong Jiang, Fen Liao, Fei Yang, Guishan Dou, Yingjie Yan, Jianhong Chen, Effects of boron on the microstructure and impact toughness of weathering steel weld metals

and existing form of boron // Materials Science and Engineering, Volume 833, 2022, № 142560

15. Zhao Y.T., Yang S.W., Guo H., Wang X.M. Rust layer structure and corrosion resistance of high-strength microalloyed // Materials Science Forum, №539-543, 2007, pp. 4774-4779.

16. Kuznetsova, A.S., Alekseev, D.Yu., Kukhta, Y.B., Emaleeva, D.G./ Prospects for the production of weather-resistant rolled steel with increased cold resistance // (2022) Chernye Metally, 2022 (3), pp. 60-64. DOI: 10.17580/chm.2022.03.11

17. Анализ актуальных направлений исследований в области производства многофункциональных материалов для экстремальных условий эксплуатации / Полецков П.П., Гулин А.Е., Емалеева Д.Г., Кузнецова А.С., Алексеев Д.Ю., Кухта Ю.Б. // Вестник Магнитогорского государственного технического университета им. Г.И. Носова. 2021. Т.19. №3. С. 109–115. <https://doi.org/10.18503/1995-2732-2021-19-3-109-115>

REAL TIME NOISE FILTERING WITH SOFTWARE FILTERS

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Abstract

In this article, I would like to discuss noise filtering from sensors. How does noise appear? What is the difference between external and internal noise? The sources and causes of noise and to discuss software filtering algorithms. Moving average filter, Adaptive moving averages filter, median filter, Kalman filter. How and when to use software filters.

Keywords: DSP, noise filtering, real time, moving average filter, adaptive moving averages filter, median filter, Kalman filter.

INTRODUCTION

The source of noise in an electronic system can be divided into two types. The first type is the noise from the sensors themselves. The second type is noise from various outside factors, most often accidental or unconnected. But no matter what the source of the noise is, it is essential we take care of the safety of the system and try to limit or prevent these problems. Measuring sensor noise is a very important process to reduce this noise.

External noise sources

As we know, correct grounding and installation of an electronic system is very important for any embedded system[1]. Incorrect grounding will cause automatic failures, measurement errors, a slowing down of some units or even the whole system as well as potential problems with instability of sensors and errors in transmitted data. In most cases, the sources of noise that are received by our electronic system, their paths and

spread, are random and therefore difficult to pinpoint. It is very difficult to measure noise because of its random nature. However, if we understand what is causing the noise, it will avoid problems in the future and permit more accurate data from our system as a whole. Most of the noise that affects our cables, sensors or boxes in which our system is encased, is conducted along ground wires in the form of current and creates a parasitic electro-magnetic field around itself which creates unwanted noise in our sensors and communication channels. Noise can also be caused by nearby equipment, power lines, switches, and external environmental factors such as lightning. Devices such as motors, relays and also switches with very rapidly changing voltage or current levels can create additional noise over a wide bandwidth. Cell phones, wi-fi, signal generators where voltage or current changes are not rapid generate noise in a narrow frequency bandwidth.

Fig1.1. Signal with Gaussian[2] and random noise.

Also one of the sources of external noise is statistical electricity. Statistical electricity appears in dielectric materials. For example, synthetic clothing and human shoes are examples of statistical electricity. It is necessary therefore to choose components carefully and be very serious about the design of the whole system, even in the design stage when using an high-quality element base to make the shortest communication channels with the highest quality shielding of wires. Analog sensors always have some noise, but the ADC (Analog to Digital convertor) integrated to the control board is usually cannot be source of noise. But this is only really effective if you connect the control board to a low-noise and high-quality power supply. If you connect it to a poor quality, power supply product you will probably get a lot of noise from the measured signal. Very often when you measure noise from a power supply, without a load, you will get a pretty decent and clear signal without background noise, but when you connect a load it can change the dynamic and this can result in noise appearing. It should be noted however

we cannot always eliminate noise using hardware tools such as filters, grounding or shielding of communication channels.

Software noise filtering

I would also like to discuss the features of software filters. They are algorithms and graphs used for digital filters. All filters are customizable. The code for these filters was written in python[3] because it is more convenient and easier to operate and achieves good functionality.. But all filters in general should written easily in any other programming language which you can use in your embedded systems.

Moving Average Filter

Explanation of a basic simple algorithm. The average[4] is the sum of values divided by the number of these values. We create a fixed buffer for the requested data from the sensor. Several earlier values are put in the buffer, and after polling the sensor, the values in the buffer are shifted, and the oldest value is removed and the new value is added.

Fig. 1.2. Is the red signal-signal without noise. The green signal-denotes added noise. The Blue signal-shows a signal after noise filtering. The moving Average Filter. Buffer size is 10 values.

As we can see, the filter is good at reducing noise. But there are also some limitations. For a significant improvement and performance acceleration of the filter it makes sense to add to the buffer a number of measurements with the power of two, in this case, the compiler will simply shift the value instead of dividing it. I also recommend to use this filter not for fast-changing

signals: because the bigger the buffer, the longer it takes to process the data, as can be seen in the following graph. There was a notable shift in the time of the signal compared to the incoming signal before the filtering was applied similarly, there were changes in the shape of the signals themselves as a result of the filtering.

Fig. 1.3. The red signal-signal without noise. The green signal-with added noise. The blue signal-a signal after noise filtering. The moving Average Filter. Buffer size is 30 values.

Adaptive Moving Averages filter

The algorithm for this filter is far simpler. We take the new value minus the already filtered value and multiply it by the coefficient. We can then adjust the coefficient by ourselves in ranges from 0.0-1.0 and the closer to 0, the smoother result we will get at the point of filter output. The exponential moving average does

not quite correctly filter out all of the sharp changes in the noise. But we can improve filter results if we make the coefficient adaptive. If there are sharp changes of values, from the previous value in the sensor, the coefficient will sharply increase, if not, then the coefficient stays the same.

Fig. 1.4. The red signal-signal without noise. The green signal-with added noise. The blue signal-a signal after noise filtering. The moving Adaptive Moving Averages filter.

Median filter

The main goal of the median[5] filter is to remove sudden changes in the signal. The median filter sorts the data from the sensor, for example, retrieves data from

all three scores from the sensor and gives us a median result. The algorithm does not calculate anything; it just compares the numbers; which makes it very fast.

Fig. 1.5. The red signal-signal without noise. The green signal-added noise. The blue signal-a signal after noise filtering. The Median filter.

As we can see from the graph, after filtering there is no shift relative to the incoming signal and it has coped perfectly well with all pulses so that when paired with other filters it performs very well and will work perfectly in most situations.

Kalman filter

The Kalman filter[6] is one of the best filters available. The idea behind this filter is to use it for collecting information about the filter object, for example, if you get data from a Hall sensor[7] on the car engine, the sudden speed jumps will be recorded and accepted by the filter and will show as a measurement error.

Fig. 1.6. The red signal-signal without noise. The green signal-added noise. The blue signal-a signal after noise filtering. Kalman filter.

CONCLUSION

In this article we discussed the causes of noise and how to filter it out. We have considered some of the physical methods of noise protection, as well as the availability software algorithms. We can say with some degree of experience that the median filter is the fastest because it doesn't calculate but only compares values. The adaptive moving averages are the most universal and will help you remove almost all noise. A moving average filter mean is slower and will not fit appropriately in situations where you get a lot of frequent data from your sensors. The Kalman filter is a good alternative with good settings but takes quite a long time to code.

References

1. Peter Marwedel, Embedded System Design: Embedded Systems Foundations of Cyber-Physical Systems 2nd ed. 2011 Edition, Springer Verlag, pp 78-90.
2. R. M. Howard, White Noise: A Time Domain Basis, 2015 International Conference on Noise and Fluctuations (ICNF).
3. Akshansh Sharma, Firoj Khan, Deepak Sharma, Dr. Sunil Gupta, Python: The Programming Language of Future, Published by Aarhus University Library Publication Volume & Issue: Volume 6, Issue 12 Page(s): 115 – 118.
4. Dr. Mahammad Abu Zalata, Dr. Musbah J. Aqel, Dr. Ziad Alqadi, Two Ways to Improve Average

and Median Filters, IJCSMC, Vol. 11, Issue. 3, March 2022, pg. 1 – 16.

5. Sebastián A. Villar, Sebastián Torcida, Gerardo G. Acosta, Median Filtering: A New Insight, Journal of Mathematical Imaging and Vision volume 58, pages130–146 (2017).

6. Qiang Li, Ranyang Li, Kaifan Ji, Wei Dai†, Kalman Filter and Its Application, 2015 8th International Conference on Intelligent Networks and Intelligent Systems, Publisher: IEEE.

7. Edward Ramsden, Hall-Effect Sensors (Second Edition) Theory and Applications, Publication date March 7, 2006, Publisher Newnes, ISBN-10 0750679344, pp 30-53.